

Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich
 Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich

Project:

BodyCom V1 - Main

Drawing number:

Rev: 1.0

Format: Laboratory: ETH - PBL

Sheet: BodyCom_V1_main.SchDoc

Date: 05/06/2024 12:46:37

A4 Q Drawn by: Lukas Schulthess

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File: C:\Users\schuluka\Desktop\PCB\BodyCom_V1\pcb\Schematics\BodyCom_V1_main.SchDoc

Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich
Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich

Project: **BodyCom V1 - MCU**

Drawing number: _____ Rev: 1.0
Date: 05/06/2024 12:46:37

Format: A4 Q Laboratory: ETH - PBL
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Sheet: BodyCom_V1_mcu.SchDoc
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M1
M2.5
M2.5 Edge Card

ETH

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Project:

BodyCom V1 - Connector

Drawing number:

Rev: 1.0

Format:

Laboratory: ETH - PBL

Sheet: BodyCom_V1_connector SchD

Date: 05/06/2024 12:46:37

A4 Q

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QVAR, Accelerometer

ETH

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Project:

BodyCom V1 - Sensors

Drawing number:

Rev: 1.0

Format: Laboratory: ETH - PBL

Sheet: BodyCom_V1_sensors.SchDoc

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Project:

BodyCom V1 - Storage

Drawing number: Rev: 1.0

Format: Laboratory: ETH - PBL

Sheet: BodyCom_V1_storage.SchDoc

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Project:
BodyCom V1 - Power

Drawing number: Rev: 1.0
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Laboratory: ETH - PBL
Drawn by: Lukas Schulthess

Sheet: BodyCom_V1_power.SchDoc
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